

Final summary of policy recommendations

Deliverable 9.2

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List of Abbreviations

AfD: Alternative für Deutschland [Alternative for Germany]

CDU: Christlich Demokratische Union [Christian Democratic Union]

CSU: Christlich-Soziale Union in Bayern [Christian Social Union in Bavaria]

CH: Switzerland

ES: Spain

DE: Germany

FIDESZ– KDNP: Fidesz Magyar Polgári Párt, Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt [Fidesz – Hungarian Civic Alliance]

FG: Focus Group

DK: Denmark

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

HU: Hungary

MKKEP: Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt

PP: Partido Popular [Spanish People's Party]

PSOE: Partido Socialista Obrero Español [Spanish Socialist Workers Party]

RWPP: Right Wing Populist Party

SPD: Sozialdemokratische Partei Deutschlands [Social Democratic Party of German]

SVP: Schweizerische Volkspartei [Swiss People's Party]

UK: United Kingdom

UKIP: United Kingdom Independence Party

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Executive summary

Deliverable 9.2 presents the findings from participatory workshops conducted in six European countries (Spain, Switzerland, Hungary, Germany, Denmark, United Kingdom) to examine how citizens experience and interpret societal challenges in their daily lives. Across diverse national contexts and participant profiles, discussions consistently centred on material concerns: healthcare and welfare provision, cost-of-living pressures, labour market insecurity, and social-media-driven polarisation—rather than cultural or identitarian issues. Participants overwhelmingly favoured solutions grounded in public intervention, including increased investment, stronger regulation, and structural reforms. Overall, 80% of recommendations fall under political action, and regulation alone comprises 44% of all proposals. Despite variations in workshop composition, core priorities converged across countries, underscoring the methodological robustness of participatory formats in capturing cross-cutting citizen insights. These results reinforce broader project evidence that mainstream parties risk losing voter trust not because of ideological distance but due to their limited responsiveness to citizens' concrete socio-economic needs

The findings demonstrate the value of embedding citizen experiences within mixed-method research and policy deliberation. Sustained investment in participatory, citizen-centred approaches will be crucial for generating high-quality scientific knowledge and informing political strategies that resonate with the lived realities of European citizens.

1. Introduction

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project “UNTWIST: Policy recommendations to regain ‘losers of feminism’ as mainstream voters”. The project aims to “un-twist” Right Wing Populist Parties (RWPP) narratives and better understand citizens’ needs, demands and worries, especially related to gender and sex. The project aims to produce actionable policy recommendations to better answer those needs and demands while promoting gender equality as a core value of the EU.

This document presents the result of the analysis of participatory workshops conducted by the consortium partners in May and June 2025 in 6 European countries: Spain, Switzerland, Hungary, Germany, Denmark and the UK. The methodology¹ and analysis of these workshops builds upon results gathered thus far in the project through different methods, including analysis of political party manifestos (WP4), of focus groups (WP2) and of a representative survey (WP8).

This report presents the results for each country, inspired by Wehn et al (2021)’s storytelling approach for policy. For each of the six countries in the project, we present some contextual elements and the workshop composition, the policy areas discussed during the sessions and key takeaways for each of the six countries of the project. We then present aggregated policy suggestions by topic and type of measure following the different national contexts, and discuss the conditions to expand this method further. In this deliverable, we provide a set of guiding principles to help policymakers and public officials develop effective strategies to address problems voiced by participants in the workshops. These principles are stemming from the workshops’ results alongside broader project outcomes, and are reflecting people’s real-life concerns and issues. Given the specific country contexts in which the workshops took place, we mostly focus here on the local findings rather than on the European level recommendations, to which the upcoming Deliverable 11.7 will be devoted.

2. Methodology

UNTWIST created a typology of gendered-based needs (Amacker, Bias, Rothermel, Nerino, 2024), which supported the design of local focus groups inviting RWPP voters to compare between present and past society, and express how they envision the future (Ortiz

¹ A more detailed explanation of the workshops’ methodology is available in Deliverable 9.1.

Barquero & Ruiz Jiménez, 2024. These findings were contextualised with a large-scale survey to analyse how social and political perceptions, especially around gender, are linked with socio-demographic characteristics (WP8). Across methodologies, the project has highlighted key issues reported across countries: health, family, education, economy, civil rights, security policies, gender norms, material inequality. The analysis of party manifestos (Carteny et al 2024) highlights that political parties do not draw attention nor clear policy directions to address these material realities or gendered needs. The analysis of demand and supply sides (Ruiz Jiménez et al, 2024) stresses that while those issues are crucial to RWPP switcher voters, they are neglected by mainstream parties as well as by right wing populist parties. Furthermore, a representative survey largely confirmed the salience of these same issues for RWPP at large. The project decided to build upon these findings to explore potential solutions to those issues through participatory workshops.

The workshops' concept was influenced by a citizen science approach, understood here as a participatory approach involving citizens in the creation of knowledge, relying especially in their everyday experience, in a way that benefits both science and society (ECSA, 2015; Hecker et al., 2019; Lorenz and Lepenies, 2023; Senabre Higaldo et al., 2021). Workshops were designed to allow residents in each of the six countries to voice their concerns and highlight concrete issues in their everyday life. This discussion was supported by statements emerging from the previous focus groups, to guide the discussion and spark ideas. Participants were encouraged to choose the topics they felt more important to discuss and propose solutions to those issues, not necessarily in the form of concrete policy propositions. Solutions could focus on the individual level (later referred to as "internal solutions") or on the political or systemic level (later referred to as "external solutions"). The discussion was facilitated to encourage diverse perspectives and ideas and understand the level of agreement on topics and solutions, but without the necessity to reach a consensus on the solutions.

A total of 12 in-person workshops took place in the six partners' countries, attended by 101 participants. All the workshops took place in the local language, therefore the quotes presented below are translated². The group composition differs across countries, as participants were not recruited following a strict sampling procedure to ensure representativity, but rather to reflect contextual specificities and scientific needs. As the next section will present, all local teams conducted mixed-gender workshops, except the UK. In most countries, participants were selected to represent the varied political spectrum that

² For the anonymised transcripts, see Blassel, R., & Ruiz Jiménez, A. M. (2025). Anonymised transcriptions of 12 participatory workshops in Spain, UK, Denmark, Germany, Hungary and Switzerland [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17831547>

composes their country's context³. In the UK, however, only RWPP switcher voters were invited, in continuity with the focus groups. The German workshop attracted only progressive women and non-binary participants with a strong interest in gender topics. The Swiss workshop gathered significantly younger participants, which also affects the topics discussed. The impact of these differences in participants' profiles will be further analysed in the discussion. While participants' number per country may seem low, the results presented here are backed by other methodologies of the projects, especially the focus groups and the survey.

3. Results: Country Recommendations

In the following sections, we present some contextual information for each country, the main policy areas discussed in the workshops and key takeaways derived from them. While comparing these outcomes with the results from the focus groups, it is important to keep in mind that focus groups only recruited people who switched from “mainstream” political parties to RWPPs.

3.1. Spain

Beginning in the mid-2000s, institutional feminism in Spain became firmly established. In the mid-2010s it was challenged and reinvigorated by protest-driven mobilisations sparked by a proposed restrictive abortion law, high-profile sexual-abuse cases, and wider cultural transformations. In the early 2020s, feminist, trans and queer movements increasingly converged around initiatives on trans rights and sexual violence, particularly those centred on consent. These developments, nonetheless, have been accompanied by a counter-reaction from radical right-wing actors, who frame such measures as expressions of “gender ideology” and as threats to what they describe as natural and traditional social order. At the time of the workshops in May 2025, Spain was not undergoing any significant socio-political events that might have affected their implementation.

The Spanish teams conducted four workshops, which took place on May 20th and 21st, 2025. Participants were recruited by the research company TARACEAS. Each workshop

³ Annex i presents for a repartition of participants in the workshops per country and party family. The classification on the political spectrum presented in this document is derived from previous classifications done in the project. For more info see Deliverable 8.1.

was moderated by three members of the UNTWIST partner team (a moderator, an assistant, and an annotator, two female and one male), and held in the facilities of Calma Research in central Madrid, in rooms equipped with comfortable furniture, sufficiently large spaces, and with the necessary materials, as well as water and sweets⁴.

In total, 32 people joined the workshops. Participants' ages ranged from 25 to 65. Each workshop included 8 participants from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds (50% from middle–high class backgrounds, 50% from working-class backgrounds), balanced in gender (50% female). Participants were not politically active and with heterogeneous political orientations (10 Spanish Socialist Workers Party - PSOE - social democrats, 13 People's Party - PP - conservative, 7 VOX - far right). There was also a balanced representation of people with families, with partners, and some single people.

3.1.1. Policy Areas

The workshops revealed a shared diagnosis of pressing socio-economic challenges, cutting across political and class divides. Participants consistently identified precarious employment, unaffordable housing, and the deterioration of public healthcare and education as the most urgent problems affecting everyday life. The difficulties faced by younger generations—particularly in achieving financial independence and accessing housing—emerged as the strongest source of collective anxiety, resonating across all age groups. Broader frustrations were also articulated regarding the perceived ineffectiveness and self-interest of political elites, signalling a widespread crisis of representation and institutional legitimacy. Housing access, cost of living, working conditions, intergenerational difficulties, and the deterioration of healthcare and education appeared as interrelated issues.

Disagreements, though present, were limited to specific policy directions rather than to the recognition of structural problems. These included diverging views on the causes of delayed youth emancipation, whether attributable to structural barriers or to individual motivation, as well as resistance to proposals involving service privatisation or excessive regulation. Nonetheless, the overarching pattern was one of pragmatic convergence, with consensus outweighing dissensus across the workshops.

Despite diverse political orientations (including supporters of PP, PSOE and VOX), participants demonstrated high levels of agreement on the nature of the problems and on

⁴ The decision to conduct the study in Madrid was due to previous unsuccessful attempts to find upper-middle-class women who voted for VOX in other locations around the rest of the country.

the need for government-led solutions. Participants consistently located the main responsibility for solutions at the governmental and political level, while occasionally pointing to the role of companies and communities. Proposed measures centred on (1) expanding affordable housing provision, improving employability and working conditions, and guaranteeing wage adequacy relative to living costs; (2) Healthcare and mental health services, with calls for more investment, greater efficiency in resource allocation, and resistance to privatisation; (3) strengthening democratic accountability, notably through professionalisation and monitoring of political representatives, as well as greater transparency in decision-making processes. While the majority of solutions were oriented towards state responsibility, some participants also recognised the role of companies and communities in alleviating socio-economic pressures.

Living conditions and welfare

“ There are people who can live comfortably on just one salary. But I can't live comfortably on one salary. So you have to work, because the bills keep coming, you need to eat, to dress, without even considering helping out the kids.”

“ And it's not just about job insecurity or access to housing, it goes much further. It fuels a social and economic gap, affects access to education, and society is becoming much more polarized in how education is perceived, etc. And above all, it strongly impacts political quality. Because in the end, if you're constantly on the tightrope of survival — which is what's happening — then you stop caring about what's going on politically, and above all, you end up paying attention to populist discourses, which is exactly what political parties are using. And so it affects how you relate to your environment, how you relate to institutions — it affects everything, and it's what's happening now. Incentivising telework with tax benefits would actually address many of the problems we've been talking about. For example, I understand that not all jobs can be done remotely, of course, but there are administrative staff, accountants who do want to be able to work from home. So, what do we do with the work in this case? The reality is that housing is expensive here, in Madrid — that's where it's expensive, in Barcelona, Madrid, the big cities, where there's a concentration of people and where all the jobs are, so everyone ends up there. If we keep overloading those population hubs, we should instead try to decentralise people and move them across Spain. Some people may have moved to a village, but who might want to come back. If we make that possible, a housing unit will be freed up, and the issue of the “emptied Spain” (la España vaciada) won't be such an issue anymore. Of course, it will still exist, but to a much lesser extent. And in those areas, the price of housing is much cheaper. Housing flexibility will be much better for people who relocate, because it's not the same paying €300,000 for a flat in Madrid as paying €30,000 for a big house in a small town. I'm just making up the numbers, but more or less that's how it goes. ”

Across the four workshops, participants demonstrated a generally high level of agreement on both the identification of key problems and the formulation of potential solutions, despite differences in political orientation. The strongest areas of consensus included concerns about current living conditions, the rising cost of goods, and, above all, the structural difficulties faced by younger generations in accessing housing and achieving independence. Agreement was also evident regarding the need for government responsibility, improved employability, corporate accountability, and measures to strengthen political representation and social fairness. Disagreements, less frequent, were mostly limited to specific policy directions (restrictions on healthcare provision, increased regulation of second-home ownership, state aid perceived as diminishing personal agency and dignity) rather than the recognition of the problems themselves. For instance regarding healthcare provisions, group 3 participants expressed disagreements. Although these were not explicitly motivated by political divisions, participants who identified as socio-democrat voters systematically proposed state intervention, while voters of RWPP opposed this intervention, preferring the privatisation of services. Mainstream right-wing voters, on the other hand, were divided in these debates. In group 4, divergence appeared during the identification of youth-related problems: while some participants stressed structural barriers preventing emancipation, others attributed late independence to a lack of effort and commitment among young people. Discussions in the workshops echo those in the focus groups, stressing strong concern about economic insecurity, rising costs of living, and difficulties in accessing housing. In both formats, participants highlight employment and labour market conditions as central challenges, linking them to family life, emancipation, and overall quality of life. Similarly, the workshops and the survey both point to housing, labour market integration, and work–life balance as pressing challenges in Spain. Across the workshops, participants repeatedly identified access to housing and precarious employment as key concerns, which closely aligns with the survey’s ranking of affordable housing and labour market integration among the most prevalent perceived challenges.

Workshops participants stressed a concern that was also highlighted in the survey: the strain of balancing employment with family responsibilities, particularly in discussions about youth emancipation and women’s caregiving burdens. In the workshops’, the discussion centered on women’s caregiving burdens and youth struggles. In the focus groups’ discussion was mainly on gendered discourse on feminism, family roles, and labour participation. While focus groups and workshops emphasised social tensions, participants do so differently: workshops underscored disagreements around youth responsibility and state support, while focus groups also portrayed tensions through criticism of subsidies, gender debates, and immigration.

The survey revealed that half of Spanish respondents are afraid of losing their social status (status-threat) and one-third feel they have lost their social status (status-loss), with gendered differences in anger, while the workshops did not frame discussions explicitly in terms of individual social status. Instead, they foregrounded material difficulties such as cost of living, job precarity and political inefficacy. Additionally, the workshops registered specific debates around the role of young people, women and minorities, whereas the survey situated inequalities more broadly by identifying groups perceived as unfairly advantaged (e.g. upper classes, refugees, LGBTQ people). While workshops described disagreements on specific policy measures (e.g., privatisation, youth culture of effort), focus groups highlighted broader ideological divides, such as attitudes toward feminism, immigration, and traditional identities.

The workshops emphasised political representation and the role of government responsibility for solutions far more than the survey, which focused instead on healthcare as the single most prevalent concern. To address economic issues, participants highlighted the need to adjust wages to living costs, enhance employability, increase corporate responsibility, strengthen broad social agreements between key actors, and promote wage equality. They also voiced the need to expand public housing, and provide family and housing aid.

Health

“I have friends, colleagues and so on, who have already started to pass away at certain ages, and you think, “wow, take care of yourself.” Because it’s true that stress can eventually give you a real scare, you know, with heart attacks and all that. People say, “but you look fine.” Sure, you look fine, but that stress—stress that our ancestors didn’t have, for whatever reason, because they lived in a different kind of society—is really taking its toll. And it’s shocking to see relatively young people, like in their forties, dying of heart attacks. “

Health appeared as a discussion topic in the workshops, but always as one issue among others rather than the top priority. Regarding welfare, and healthcare in particular, participants voiced the need to improve healthcare through more contracts and better resource management, while avoiding privatisation. Participants supported increased investment in mental health care and education, as well as improved pension and tax systems.

Democratic responsibility

“I find that it would be ideal to have a political class that we would like to resemble, to have role models. Blimey, it’s that I’d like to be like him, well, let’s say because of his fair play, how he loves his political enemy, how he allies himself despite thinking very differently on many things but looking for what one does think the same about for a benefit to the population [...]”

“For me we have a political class that is not professional. I mean, the practice of politics should be professionalised.”

Participants were generally unsatisfied with current politics, and suggested improving political representation through professionalisation, transparency, and monitoring of public officers. Distrust in political elites and frustration with representation expressed in the workshops resonates with the survey’s findings on widespread perceptions of unfair advantage among upper classes, as well as the proportion of population aligning with RWPP positions. Similar to focus group participants, workshop participants expressed distrust or criticism toward political elites and government efficacy, framing politicians as ineffective or self-serving. Despite these criticisms, workshops mainly attribute responsibility for change to government and decision-makers. Focus groups, on the other hand, emphasise criticism of state intervention itself (e.g., subsidies, quotas) and reveal populist, anti-elitist sentiments. These differences are strongly linked with the composition, since focus groups consisted of switcher voters of the radical right (VOX) who had previously voted for mainstream parties or abstained, while workshops were more heterogeneous, including voters from the radical right, the mainstream right and left.

3.1.2. Takeaways

Workshops were well received by participants: despite initial scepticism, they voiced hope and enthusiasm to have a practical impact on policy and reach policymakers. It must be noted, however, that in most groups, participants from higher social classes with greater cultural capital or higher educational levels tended to dominate the conversation, despite the moderators’ efforts to encourage more balanced participation.

When compared with other research instruments, workshops mirrored survey results in highlighting housing and employment as central concerns, while also aligning with focus groups in their criticism of political elites. However, workshops were more solution-oriented, producing specific and actionable proposals, whereas focus groups revealed deeper cultural and identity-based polarisation. The workshops thus provided a unique space

where heterogeneous citizens could identify common ground and collectively formulate pathways for reform.

From these discussions, several policy recommendations can be distilled:

- **Expand public and affordable housing provision:** Increasing the availability of affordable housing, especially for young people.
- **Improve employability and working conditions:** Developing policies that promote stable, well-compensated employment and equal opportunities across sectors and territories along the country.
- **Increase investment in healthcare and mental health.**
- **Increase transparency and accountability in governance and public administration processes:** Ensuring that decision-making procedures are clear, accessible, and accountable to the public.
- **Professionalise public service and political functions to strengthen institutional capacity and governance quality.**
- **Enhance resource management and efficiency:** Optimizing the allocation and use of public resources to ensure maximum social impact and sustainability.
- **Improve coordination across levels of government and simplify administrative processes:** Enhancing coordination between local, regional, and national governments to streamline services and reduce bureaucratic inefficiencies making use of digital technologies.

3.2. Switzerland

The Swiss political system reflects its federal structure: power is shared between the Confederation (the federal government), the cantons and the municipalities. The cantons are constituent states of the Swiss Confederation and each of the 26 cantons has a high degree of autonomy (e.g. on education, healthcare and policing). They have their own constitution, parliament, government and courts. Switzerland's system of direct democracy is widely regarded by its citizens as a defining and exceptional feature of the country's political system. Beyond electing representatives, citizens regularly vote on issues at local, cantonal, and federal levels, allowing them to challenge parliamentary decisions and

propose amendments to the Federal Constitution. This strong tradition of civic participation is a point of national pride and central to how political legitimacy is understood in Switzerland. The SVP (Swiss People's Party) is the largest and most influential political party in Switzerland represented in both parliament (25-30% vote share since the late 1990s, which is consistently growing) and government (since 2003 it holds two out of seven seats). It is a national-conservative and right-wing populist party considered to be more right-wing than the German AfD. The SVP has led numerous anti-immigrant and populist referenda and initiatives and serves as an inspiration for many right-wing populist parties in Europe. More recently, they have also started politicising gender, with "gender-terror" and "woke-insanity" now being one of the issues addressed in their party manifesto 2023-2027.

Despite Switzerland not being part of the European Union, European and EU-national politics, especially those of countries close to Switzerland such as Germany, are very relevant for Switzerland. The workshop took place after Trump's re-election and shortly after the German Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution agency classified the AfD as "confirmed right-wing extremist" which, a few days later, was contested by the AfD, which was followed by a 'standstill commitment', meaning that the Agency put the official reclassification on hold until the legal disputes are resolved. Both of these political events were discussed extensively within the digital sphere. This might have had an influence on how pressing the issue of social media and misinformation was to the participants. The German context and news of the AfD designation was also specifically referenced by one participant at the beginning of the discussion.

The Swiss team conducted one workshop, on May 9th 2025. Participants were recruited through a survey sent out to all students at the University of Bern through the administrative office and via other institutions. This caused the group to be more homogenous in terms of age and socio-economic status than in the focus groups. Heterogeneity was sought along other variables, in particular political orientation. The workshop was moderated by two female members of the project's team, and was held in a seminar room of the main building of the University of Bern, in a building which is not connected to specific faculties so that participants would not feel as outsiders simply because of the location itself.

The workshop gathered 8 participants, 4 women and 4 men, all aged between 22 and 27. All participants were currently involved in their studies (4 Bachelor's degree, 4 Master's degree, mostly in social science and humanities), 2 were unemployed, 5 were working part-time less than 50%, and one person part-time more than 50%. A preliminary survey allowed the creation of a heterogenous group with self-assessed left- and right-wing as well as more centrist people, and people who voted differently in three recent popular votes

(Responsible Business Initiative for human rights and environmental regulations for Swiss-based companies, same-sex marriage, and paternity leave⁵). More specifically, workshop participants were asked to place themselves on a 1 (far left) to 10 (far right) scale: two participants placed themselves at 7 on the left–right scale (right-leaning), one of whom explicitly stated that they voted for the SVP in the most recent elections. Three participants positioned themselves at 5 (centrist); among them, one reported voting for the Greens (Grüne, GPS), while another mentioned not having voted in the last electoral round. One participant positioned themselves at 3 and did not vote in the last elections. Finally, two participants placed themselves at 1 (left-leaning); one voted for the Social Democrats (SP), while the other could not recall their vote.

3.2.1. Policy Areas

The discussion focused on: (1) the dangers of social media (especially for children and youth) because of the spread of misinformation and the absence of any regulations on it and (2) the polarisation in society, social media and politics as something negative which results in an inability to lead civil discussions between people with differing opinions. (3) Family policies were the only topic discussed with a strong gender connotation.

Social media

“I think you can see it very clearly in the election results among younger generations. It shows that young people tend to vote more extremely. [...] Everyone has an algorithm and if you already hold a certain opinion, you might follow the parties that share that opinion. Then you end up in these bubbles and get news and other things according to them. This way, you become much more extreme in your thinking because once you are in this Trump-bubble, that is all you see all day long and you get all kinds of fake news and stuff. [...] I think it’s a huge issue that is also taking root everywhere. And I think that it’s discussed far too little in politics. Nowhere in any [election programme] does it say that they want to tackle this issue in any way. I find that very, very interesting.”

Social media was described as dangerous, especially for children. Participants discussed the existence of echo chambers on social media, which fuel extreme opinions and divisions. They criticised the overrepresentation of “loud minorities” and of US, China and Russia on content and through platform ownership. Participants blamed both a lack of regulations and a lack of critical thinking from users.

⁵ While the two latter votes connect to gender politics, the first was highly contested and thus might also give an idea of participants’ political views.

The workshop participants shared with the focus group participants the sentiment that it is especially young people who are influenced by social media. Participants agreed on the need for regulations or legal consequences for misbehaviour, or any kind of state intervention in how social media currently works.

The discussion pointed to the following elements to restrain the dangers caused by social media: regulations could be introduced to reduce anonymity online; legal consequences could be applied to sanction online misbehaviour. Teaching how to use media and learn to identify false information in schools was promoted as a responsibility of the state. The “*abolishment*” of social media was suggested by one participant, but other participants reacted to this by arguing that this would be a form of censorship which could be problematic. The group then argued for the “*depoliticisation*” of social media instead. This discussion suggests the need for further discussion on the pros and cons of state intervention regarding online communication.

Polarisation in society

“There is polarisation on social media, but there are also so many smaller influences that you simply don’t notice [on social media]. [...] You might see a short video about something, and you won’t even realise that it might be fake news and then you carry that into reality. There are so many small influences that you can’t really control. And that’s why I think there is a connection. I think there are also many young people who nowadays read [...] news on social media and get their information there. That’s why it’s even more important to be able to find the right information there.”

Participants discussed a growing tendency to extreme opinions within society (among others through social media “*bubbles*”), the inability to have discussions between people with differing opinions, as well as the inability to voice opinions without getting criticised or ostracised. They blame this lack of discussion on “*echo chambers*” and political “*bubbles*”, but also on political actors’ focus on short-term wins instead of long-term changes.

The discussion on polarisation echoes discussions in the male-only focus group in Work Package 2, which also highlighted the role of digitalisation in the rise of populism. Like the workshop participants, focus group participants agreed that digitalisation and the issues it brings have largely remained unaddressed by Swiss politics. Workshops participants agreed on the potential of education to make a difference in how (young) people form their opinions and perceive information online and beyond. Polarisation can also be addressed through consensus democracy, by creating new flexible regulations or laws. There was consensus that state intervention to constrain polarisation was needed. The state was also seen as responsible for shifting the logic of online and offline discourse away from populist rhetoric. Long term investments or projects should aim for the general good rather than

short term electoral or financial wins. In the discussions, polarisation can be addressed through reforming the educational system, increasing investment in education (more resources and support), while also increasing the focus on critical thinking, supporting discussion culture and important life learnings while censoring political opinions of teachers. Workshop and focus groups participants shared the general sentiment of unhappiness with the educational system. Workshop participants repeatedly mentioned the need for more critical thinking (especially among young people) and that young people should be taught more critical thinking skills. For workshop participants, it should be the responsibility of the state to educate young people, while focus groups participants did not agree on whose role this is (e.g. family or state). While for the focus group participants this was more about scope of taught content, growing pressure and lack of time and discipline, the workshop participants mentioned the issue of politicisation through teachers and lecturers sharing their political opinions and trying to influence their students. The workshop participants identified educating children as a very important theme, while education in Switzerland was not one of the main issues in the survey.

Gender through family policies

“The frame should be such that individual needs can be considered and that there is a certain degree of flexibility. Whether that's for family structures or whether that's maternity leave, for example. [...] But there has to be a frame, a limitation, so to speak. If I think of [a possible] solution, it would be to decide that there is one year of time... of leave after the birth, and that can be divided between the mother and father as they wish or also for same-sex couples. That would then include everyone, all flexibilities – that is, all individualities or individual family models. If you say that the mother gets a year, but then you have, for example, two men who adopt a newborn, they each only get their two weeks. [...] If you then have that frame that the family simply gets a year off, or holiday, that would create solutions that have a clear limit, but are adaptable to individual needs.”

Although two of the discussion prompts referred explicitly to gender or gender-related issues, participants tended not to select these as their priorities. Instead, most chose other statements to guide the discussion, resulting in a conversation that rarely centered on gender concerns—except when family policy was addressed. When nudged, participants revealed a rather progressive understanding of sexuality as well as an acceptance of women's inclusion in the labour market. This was particularly interesting given the strong anti-left or anti-“woke” consensus in the rest of the discussion. This also repeated a theme that emerged in the focus groups, whereby participants seem to agree with a lot of emancipatory and essentially feminist content but do not associate it with feminism or progressive views.

Participants said they were unsatisfied with the current form of maternity and parental leave in Switzerland, and criticised pressures for women to work or stay at home after giving birth. One participant voiced concerns about the erosion of the family. A form of moral panic around the family was also described as constructed and contributing to polarisation.

To improve family policies, participants suggested creating a flexible system which would allow for individual choices, for instance by promoting parental leave flexibly for same-sex parents as well as between mothers and fathers. They stressed that policies should focus on humans instead of on costs and economy. Policies should promote opportunities for all genders to work according to their preferences and abilities without external pressures, for instance by providing more protection during pregnancy and motherhood.

While the sentiment that feminism is going too far was shared among both focus group and workshop participants, workshop participants nonetheless acknowledged that there are inequalities regarding gender and sexuality. For some of the focus group participants (this was contested by another participant) feminism in Switzerland is no longer about strengthening women but about abolishing any gender differences. The focus group participants argued that either gender equality has been achieved or that the feminist movement is too extreme. In the workshops, feminism was rarely mentioned, but it came up several times in the context of the “*left*” as an extreme movement. Interestingly, this was not about the content of gender equality goals (which they agreed with in particular in terms of family policy), but rather in terms of discussion culture and rhetoric which some participants perceived as too harsh and uncompromising, thus contributing to polarisation. This sentiment was, however, not shared among all participants.

Other topics

It is important to note that the workshop focused on participants’ everyday experiences and issues that affect them directly. Therefore, topics such as childcare, family roles, workplace, healthcare or the pension system, were not discussed by workshop participants, who, given their age and their professional status, do not have any experience with those issues. On the other hand, those topics were important for more senior focus groups participants. Additionally, workshop participants also did not discuss migration and the asylum system which played an important role in the focus group discussions. In addition to the demographic profiles, this can be linked to the differences in political orientations, as the focus groups included only people who switched their votes to RWPPs (or back), whereas the workshop did not include people who strongly identify as RWPP voters. Generally, we found an interest and awareness of workshop participants about the importance of political

rhetoric and discourse for societal change (which was also reflected by the topics discussed) that was more pronounced than among the participants of the focus groups.

3.2.2. Takeaways

Despite the presence of individuals who identified as more left-leaning, the overall discussion mostly reflected conservative-leaning opinions. As such, the workshop seemed to mirror both current research on the higher propensity to vote for right-wing parties of young people (Abou-Chadi, 2024) as well as the broader mainstreaming of far-right ideas. Participants did not seem to perceive conservative party politics' responsibility in amplifying rather than mitigating the aspects that were mentioned as problems (polarisation, populist rhetoric, "free" internet, restriction on paternity leave etc.).

Overall, workshop participants were strong supporters of state intervention. Censorship was also evoked, before being nuanced, highlighting the fine balance between limiting harassment and misinformation and limiting free speech. The discrepancy between support for gender equality policies and a widespread although not universal rejection of actors advocating for these policies seems to indicate that gender is indeed a 'twisted' topic. The far-right discourse about cancel culture has led to a twisted climate about wide-spread misunderstandings of a) feminism/gender politics and b) freedom of speech/polarisation, which seems to have reached across all our participants. The workshop showed that differences between younger (workshop) and older (focus groups) conservative participants are more limited than anticipated, as the women focus group participants and student participants acknowledged positive aspects of progressive gender politics while rejecting feminism.

We can derive the following policy recommendations:

- **Extend the post-partum recovery period and improve access to mental-health services:** this would include systematic detection and support for post-partum depression, and increase practical and psychosocial support for families during and after childbirth.
- **Introduce a one-year parental leave scheme:** it would need to be flexibly shared across all family types (including same-sex and adoptive families), while legally recognising the specific biological recovery needs associated with childbirth.
- **Improving critical-thinking skills and civic education:** needed to equip citizens with the ability to understand and advocate for better public goods, including

infrastructure and social services. Participants supported reforms in schooling and early education that contribute indirectly to future work–family balance, helping children develop resilience and critical thinking.

- **Safeguarding freedom of speech:** while also navigating the perniciousness of (online) polarisation (discussion on cancel culture).

3.3. Hungary

Since the focus groups conducted in 2023, Hungary’s political landscape has undergone a significant transformation. A turning point came with a complex domestic political crisis in February 2024, which led to the emergence of a new political party, TISZA (conservative), by the 2024 European Parliament elections. The new party has since continued to grow in influence and has the potential to win the 2026 parliamentary elections.

The Hungarian team conducted two workshops in Hungary, the first in Miskolc on 26 May 2025, followed by the second workshop in Budapest on 27 May 2025. The choice of Budapest and Miskolc as locations provided a contrast between Hungary’s capital and one of its significant regional cities, allowing for comparative insights across different urban contexts. Miskolc and its surrounding area are characterised by the impact of post-socialist transformation: while the city was a major industrial centre during the socialist era, it has faced various economic and infrastructural challenges since the regime change. The region is also notable for having a relatively high concentration of Roma population, which constitutes an important factor in local social tensions and political dynamics. At the time of the workshop, there was no major domestic or international political news with the potential to influence the course of the discussions. Both workshops have been moderated by two members of the UNTWIST research team at the Centre for Social Sciences.

In total, 16 people joined the workshops. The first workshop was composed of eight participants (four men and four women) residing in Budapest. The second mirrored this composition with an equal number of male and female participants from Miskolc. All participants in both workshops had a secondary level of education and were currently employed. This criterion was selected to reflect the views of the working middle class, a key demographic in Hungarian society. Additionally, all participants were parents, which added another layer of shared life experience, enriching the discussions with perspectives on family-related issues, work-life balance, and public services. Importantly, the political composition of the groups was deliberately mixed. Each workshop included four individuals

who had voted for the governing Fidesz-KDNP party in the 2022 parliamentary elections, and four who had supported one of the opposition parties (6 Jobbik Momentum MSZP - LMP Párbeszéd, 2 Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt - MKKP).

3.3.1. Policy Areas

In Miskolc, participants decided to focus on the topics of financial situation and inequalities, healthcare, generational dynamics, and public safety. Although all four were discussed, the issue of financial hardship and inequality dominated the session, not necessarily because it was deemed most important, but due to time constraints and the participants' strong initial engagement with the topic. In contrast, participants in Budapest chose to focus on financial situations and inequalities, healthcare, children's lifestyle, and social welfare services. Here too, while there was broad interest in all selected themes, the conversation was particularly weighted toward financial insecurity, healthcare, and the state of welfare services, issues widely perceived as urgent and indicative of deeper systemic challenges in Hungarian society.

Across the Miskolc and Budapest workshops, participants explored not only the key social challenges affecting their lives but also actively generated a range of proposed solutions. These proposals fell into two broad categories: external solutions, typically understood as the responsibility of the state and other institutional actors; and internal solutions, reflecting actions individuals or communities might undertake on their own. While both types were present in each discussion, a strong emphasis was placed on external, state-led solutions—especially regarding systemic issues like economic inequality, healthcare, and social welfare. Participants often framed these solutions in terms of fairer policymaking, equitable resource distribution, and a more effective and accountable public sector. The few instances where internal solutions were more prominent, such as in the area of public safety, suggest that when state interventions are perceived as limited or ineffective, citizens are more likely to emphasize personal responsibility and local-level actions.

Financial situation and inequalities

"We forgot to mention the need to create jobs for people with intellectual disabilities, and support for blind people, meaning the creation of workplaces for them. I think this is also important, because I regularly see blind people begging. They're probably not doing it because they're well taken care of or have great jobs. These days, even pens are assembled by machines. In the past, for example, blind people used to do that kind of work, or people with hip or spinal problems could work part-time. And now there are no part-time jobs available — not even for someone

who has a seriously ill child and would need to work reduced hours alongside caregiving."

In Miskolc, discussions highlighted that most pressing problems required structural interventions. Regarding financial inequalities, participants proposed progressive taxation, increasing the minimum wage, providing state-sponsored training opportunities, and reintroducing seniority-based wage supplements. Though internal solutions such as self-development and side jobs were also mentioned, some participants notably expressed that no meaningful internal solutions existed without supportive public policies, underscoring the perceived limits of individual agency in the face of systemic inequality.

In the Budapest workshop, participants approached the topics with a similarly pragmatic lens, proposing both policy reforms and personal actions—but often as a response to perceived state dysfunction. On financial inequalities, suggested external interventions included reducing VAT, introducing progressive income taxation, and removing state incentives that distort the housing market. Internally, participants cited actions like job mobility, retraining, and frugal consumption.

Healthcare

"So the state is obliged to support the legitimacy of screening programs and help us eat more healthily — by setting prices accordingly, for example by lowering VAT, so that we can actually afford access to these kinds of foods."

"Screening programs should be free and accessible everywhere; healthy eating, regular exercise, and participation in screenings should be supported — potentially through public healthcare funding or social insurance. Healthcare workers' wages, private healthcare, and professional training are lacking. There's aging, funding cuts, doctor shortages and instead of stadiums, investment should go into private healthcare."

"Well, we proposed that the state should support healthcare and expand public health insurance funding, so that people don't have to rely on unaffordable private healthcare for examinations. [...] Another point raised was that if private healthcare services are provided, employers should receive some kind of support — for example, if an employer offers private healthcare to an employee, they should receive a tax benefit or some form of incentive."

Disapproval of long medical waiting lists was unanimous, seen as a clear failure of the healthcare system. In the Miskolc workshop, external solutions to issues with healthcare included significant state reinvestment, increased staffing and better wages, and policy reforms such as guaranteed access to a free choice of doctor. Internal solutions—like turning to private care or maintaining a healthier lifestyle—were mentioned but seen as insufficient or inaccessible for many. In the Budapest workshop, while the focus was again

on substantial public investment and wage increases in the sector, citizens also proposed individual health-conscious behaviours such as diet and exercise.

Welfare services

"We proposed the expansion of social welfare services and an increase in the benefit amounts. There are certain social benefits whose amounts haven't increased in years. We also mentioned support for home care."

When addressing the welfare system, participants stressed the need for expanded state care infrastructure and improved benefits, while internal coping strategies such as multi-generational living and personal savings were also discussed, albeit sometimes reluctantly or with ambivalence. When discussing intergenerational issues, participants largely called for more equal treatment by the state across age groups, such as abolishing age-based tax exemptions and expanding family benefits more fairly. Internal solutions were notably lacking, with several groups unable to identify any.

The topic of children's lifestyle yielded a balanced mix of external proposals—such as state-supported sports and healthier school meals—and internal actions like spending more family time and limiting screen use.

Parental responsibility was strongly emphasised. While both internal and external solutions were proposed, the overall consensus was that systemic problems need systemic answers, though individuals are often left to adapt when public systems fall short.

Public safety

"Or for example, neighbors helping each other out. There are really useful posts on Facebook, like 'I saw this car here and there, it stopped and was watching,' and then half the village is already looking out the window—so the person has no chance. This is what I mean: a kind of self-defense where people support each other on this level. Maybe that black car only stopped because they like my house, but we're already operating like a warning network. This is the kind of self-defense we had in mind. Not the kind where, if a 120-kilo guy comes at me, I can actually do much about it—obviously I'll kick and bite... But I think self-defense should also mean prevention: teaching our kids not to become victims, to try to avoid these situations if they can." (Male, Hungary, Miskolc)

Public safety prompted more community-level suggestions such as self-defence training and neighbourhood watch programs, though these were accompanied by calls for better police funding and stronger law enforcement. This marked a shift from the often-cited external solutions to internal ones.

3.3.2. Takeaways

The workshops in Miskolc and Budapest reflected a shared understanding of the need for systemic responses to pressing social challenges, particularly around financial insecurity, healthcare, and social welfare. In Miskolc, participants strongly emphasised the state's responsibility, especially regarding fairness in policy and universal support. While internal solutions were mentioned—particularly for public safety—participants largely agreed on the need for state-led change. No major disagreements emerged, with minor differences stemming from individual experiences or interpretations of past policies. In Budapest, consensus was also broad, especially on the role of the state in managing economic and healthcare issues. However, when it came to social welfare, views began to diverge - even though not following party lines. While some saw home-based care as a partial solution, others rejected this as insufficient and stressed that it remains a core responsibility of the state. Across both locations, participants showed a willingness to accept some individual responsibility—especially where state systems are weak—but consistently called for more inclusive and equitable public policies.

Overall, there are strong similarities between the key findings of the workshops and the previous focus group discussions. While workshop participants seemed less keen to stress decline in values as symptoms of a disintegrating social fabric than focus group participants, they still voiced frustration with widening inequality, low wages, inflation, and housing inaccessibility. Both women's and men's focus groups put a stronger emphasis on security, violence and crime, as well as changing family and gender roles. Interestingly, while focus group participants showed deep scepticism about government economic policy, especially regarding high taxes, the destruction of domestic industry, and fears about future pensions, workshops' participants still identified the state as the main actor of change. In both workshops and focus groups, men and women were critical of the current radical right family policies, especially regarding taxation, which is interesting because focus group participants were switcher voters. Workshops participants voiced the same claim as both male and female focus groups regarding Hungary's healthcare system as being in crisis—highlighting long wait times, unclean hospital conditions, and a dual system where public care is undermined by doctors' reliance on private practices. Expecting solutions from the state was apparent in both focus groups and workshops in Hungary. Focus group results are more detailed on gender-based needs, while in the workshops gender issues emerged only indirectly, related to family policies.

According to what emerged instead from the survey, the top three challenges perceived by Hungarian respondents related to good healthcare, affordable housing and social services,

and balancing employment and family. The rank order was similar for both men and women, with one equally important additional factor for women: integration into the labour market. Therefore, we can state that the results of the workshop and the survey are well in accordance.

However, some differences manifested among workshop results and those of the survey. In the survey subjective assessment of the financial situation of the respondent and social inequalities was not assessed whereas in the workshop it was at the top of the list. However, in the Hungarian survey upper class members were recognised as the most unfairly advantaged social group, hinting dissatisfaction with social equality. Moreover, indirectly balancing paid employment and family duties and integrating successfully into the labour market (recorded as the third and fourth most important challenges in the survey) could also negatively impact financial situation and inequalities as reflected in the workshop. Challenges linked to raising and educating children and being physically safe occurred with a moderate frequency in the survey, while it was prioritised in the workshop.

The group evenly included participants who had voted for the governing coalition and others who had supported the opposition in the last election (three years ago). The discussion showed virtually no sign of political polarisation or division: all participants expressed frustration and dissatisfaction. Only few explicit political references were made against specific governmental policies, however no participant voiced strong support for the government's policies, and it could be observed that opposition voters were more frequently taking the role of spokesperson than supporters of the governing coalition.

From the discussion, the following policy recommendations can be derived:

- **Financial inequalities:** progressive income tax, increasing the minimum wage, providing state-sponsored training opportunities, and reintroducing seniority-based wage supplements, reducing VAT, and removing state incentives that distort the housing market.
- **Healthcare:** significant public investment, increased staffing, wage increases in the sector and policy reforms such as guaranteed access to a free choice of doctor. Additionally, individual health-conscious behaviours such as diet and exercise as health prevention activities could be promoted. To ensure children's healthy lifestyle, state-supported sports and healthier school meals could be subsidised.

- **Social welfare system:** there is a need for expanded state care infrastructure and improved benefits and allowances, as well as policies limiting overtime work for parents to be able to spend more time with family.
- **Intergenerational issues:** more equal treatment by the state across age groups, such as abolishing age-based tax exemptions and expanding family benefits more fairly.
- **Public safety:** self-defence training, neighbourhood watch programs, better police funding and stronger law enforcement.

It is interesting to note that RWPPs policies, such as reducing social assistance, while introducing flat-rate income tax and specific tax credits for families and pensioners (Rathgeb, 2024 ; Elsässer & Röth, 2025 ; Greilinger & Mudde, 2024) is criticised by participants, although half declared having voted for the ruling government.

3.4. Germany

In spring 2025, Germany was in a period of political transition: following the federal elections, there was a new middle-right coalition with Christian Democratic Union (CDU)/Christian Social Union in Bavaria (CSU) (conservative, right) and the Social Democratic Party (SPD) (social democrat). The country was facing low growth, high living costs and increasing pressure on families and public services. Gender equality was a highly polarised issue: progressive parties emphasised equal pay, reforms to parental leave and childcare, while conservatives and the far right focused on traditional family roles and opposed 'gender ideology', especially regarding gendered language which is banned in some counties. The radical right Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) is stronger than ever before, with a clear anti-feminist agenda. The workshop took place ahead of Christopher Street Day, Germany's annual celebration and demonstration for LGBTQ+ rights, which is also a major topic of discussion.

The German workshop took place on May 27th, 2025. Participants were recruited through various channels, including social media, newspaper advertisements and networking activities. The workshop were facilitated by 3 female moderators (2 from UNTWIST project and one from the host institution) and took place in the FrauenGenderBibliothek, a non-profit library which aims to promote gender equality and comprehensive minority rights by providing the public with a wide range of expertise and up-to-date information on these topics. It is a place of active integration and networking for women's politics' and thus a

place that not only provides space for discussions on gender and equality, but also supports them. It could be that the place of the workshop was the reason why the overall atmosphere was leaning towards the feminist side from the beginning. The fact that the location is positively biased towards equality may have deterred negative voices. The name could have been the reason why there were only women and non-binary people, because men might not feel included in “gender” topics and excluded by “women”.

The workshop gathered a total of 11 female and non-binary participants, who were divided in three groups, each consisting of 3-4 participants. Ages ranged from 20 to 75, with an average age of 45. Two participants were currently students, eight were employed and one was currently unemployed, while ten of the participants had a university degree or secondary education. Marital status is unknown; some had children, but most participants did not indicate that they were parents. None of the participants were politically active. Their political orientation was generally left-wing/green/alternative, with a few conservative views, although we did not gather precise data on participants’ political positioning. It is important to stress that the German workshop did not include RWPP voters, we therefore cannot assume that these voters would support all the proposed solutions.

3.4.1. Policy Areas

Overall, there was a high level of agreement due to relatively homogeneous political views, but with greater enthusiasm for certain topics. The discussions focused on gender roles and stereotypes, the unequal distribution of care responsibilities and structural inequalities in the labour market. Participants reported on their personal experiences with societal expectations that mothers should give up their studies or work, the lack of institutional support for student parents and the unequal acceptance of fathers who take on parental responsibilities. Another discussed topic was feminism and emancipation when some participants criticised women for having ‘resigned themselves’ to their roles, while others pointed to systemic constraints. The lack of childcare places and the compatibility of work and family life emerged as key issues. Participants also discussed the reproduction of stereotypes in schools and kindergartens, the need for gender-sensitive education, and the growing influence of conservative tendencies in social media. Some groups linked gender inequality to capitalism, low wages and high living costs.

Most of these topics were raised spontaneously, while the moderators encouraged participants to develop them into actionable recommendations. Other topics identified were entrenched stereotypes, unequal pay, pension gaps due to longer parental leave for women, and limited recognition of care work. Several noted the absence of systematic

training for educators in gender sensitivity, leading to the continued reproduction of stereotypes in schools. Media and social media were perceived as amplifying inequality, with trends such as “tradwives” encouraging traditional roles. These problems were mostly raised spontaneously, although moderators ensured that issues such as sexualised violence and media representation were also addressed. There was slight disagreement about whether some women rely too much on their role as housewives. This point was not discussed further but it was suggested that this should be seen less as an active decision on the part of women and more as a situation determined by their social role.

While the entire workshop discussion was gender-related, this was not the case with the focus groups (FG). However, even though the moderator had to actively ask questions, both the FG and the workshops discussed gender-neutral language and role models. In the FG, role models were mainly discussed by women. There was broad agreement on gender-specific issues within the focus groups (negative attitude) and within the workshop (positive attitude). Regarding family dynamics and role models, the female FG and the workshop share acknowledgements of the emancipation and the necessity for shared responsibilities. Both highlighted difficulties in raising children due to economic insecurities. We can note a bigger difference between the two focus groups (male group and female group) than between the three groups of the workshop. Although the female FG supported the past achievements of feminism and emancipation, they also expressed gender fatigue, saying where we are in the right direction but complaining about feminism as a movement against men rather than simply advocating for women's rights and criticising a too politicised feminist movement. The focus group participants saw gender-neutral language as useless, wrong, and excessive, and shared a feeling of gender fatigue, while the workshop groups talked positively about gender related topics.

The survey identified a few “losers of feminism” who feel disadvantaged by feminist progress, most of whom were RWPP voters. The workshop participants did not view feminism as something negative and therefore did not identify as “losers of feminism” (while being women and no RWPP voters). A major finding of the survey, the gendered collective identity, was not addressed in the workshop

The greatest agreement among workshop’s participants was on the following points: (1) the need for more childcare places and easier access, equal pay and pension reform, (2) compulsory gender-sensitive education, equal acceptance of the caregiving role of fathers.

Family, care, and labour market

“When I got pregnant back then, everyone around me agreed that I should drop out of university”

“With a 40-hour week, you hardly have any time left to think about yourself, your roles and your life.”

“Then we're back to capitalism, and I don't think we can overturn that today.”

Participants criticised the lack of affordable childcare places, inflexible work models, and long working hours, which reinforce traditional gender divisions. The proposed solutions included equal or shared parental leave, a pension reform and a significant expansion of childcare facilities. Participants called for equal pay, higher salaries in care professions, and more male role models in early childhood education.

Gendered roles, stereotypes, education and awareness

“And then you just do it without questioning it, because that's how it's supposed to be and that's what you see everywhere, in the media, often in your parents' home, in other relationships you see.”

Participants proposed integrating gender-sensitive teaching into teacher training and promoting closer cooperation with parents. Media-related proposals included public funding for inclusive productions and stricter regulation of harmful online content. Some of these measures, such as the expansion of childcare or the introduction of compulsory teacher training, were suggested by the moderators inspired by what was said in the discussion and then confirmed and finalised by the participants, while others, e.g. the 25-hour working week and pension reforms, were spontaneously proposed by the participants. We only report below on solutions that were thoroughly discussed, not on those that were not only mentioned in side notes.

3.4.2. Takeaways

The workshops in Germany revealed strong concerns about persistent gender inequalities in family life, work and education. Participants highlighted structural barriers such as unequal parental leave arrangements, insufficient childcare, gender stereotypes in schools and the influence of the media and social media. While many solutions were raised spontaneously, the moderators helped to focus the discussions on concrete recommendations. In all groups, participants expressed frustration at the slow pace of change and called for systemic reforms, particularly in the areas of childcare, education and equal pay. Overall, the workshop highlighted how discussion can contribute to a better

and deeper understanding. In this case, this is true when people are not too far apart in their original moral orientation. However, the workshop leaves open the question of how different it would have been with a more diverse group. The moderation itself presented a challenge, more intensive training should have been provided, or experienced moderators should have been employed.

We can identify four main areas in which we were able to formulate explicit policy measures. These recommendations underline that both systemic reforms and cultural change are essential to advance gender equality in Germany. However, we cannot assume that RWPP voters would support those policies.

- **In the area of family and care:** reforms should introduce mandatory 50/50 parental leave, ensure pension protection during parental leave, and expand access to affordable childcare.
- **In the labour market:** enforcing equal pay and working time reforms are key to achieving balance.
- **In the area of education and awareness-raising:** mandatory gender-sensitive training and better recognition and pay for childcare professions are needed.
- **Media and regulation:** inclusive representation should be promoted through subventions and incentives, while harmful online content and stereotypes must be subject to stricter oversight.

3.5. Denmark

In early summer 2025 Denmark was in a relatively calm political context, with no major domestic political events affecting the discussions during this period. Denmark was governed by a centre-right coalition of the Social Democrats, Venstre (liberals), and Moderates (liberals). The coalition struggled with internal defections, in particular the Moderate party, and limited legislative progress and reforms. In terms of international context, this period was marked by geopolitical tensions around Greenland, Ukraine and Palestine. Denmark was about to take over the EU Council Presidency.

The Danish workshop took place on June 2nd in Esbjerg and June 3rd, 2025 in Roskilde. The dates, just before the summer holiday period, meant that there were no immediate electoral campaigns or major policy announcements. *The regional contexts of both Esbjerg, in Western Jutland, and Roskilde, in mid-Zealand, were relevant in providing different*

dimensions of Denmark: industrial concerns and scepticism of Danish and EU politics more prominent in Esbjerg, while the workshop in Roskilde was more characterised by the cosmopolitan, progressive outlook of the Greater Copenhagen region.

Participants were recruited using a range of methods, from social media advertisement to direct connections with civil society groups and previous connections, reaching out to participants of the focus groups. The moderation team consisted of a male post-doc (Swedish/American), a female student assistant (Danish), and a female PI (Danish/German) from the UNTWIST team. This diversity was readily accepted by the workshop participants. Both workshops were held in neutral, public spaces for organising the workshops. The Esbjerg workshop took place at the public library, located in the centre of Esbjerg. The library is spacious and inviting, with good facilities and easy access for all participants. The Copenhagen workshop was held at 'Byens Hus', a municipal community centre in central Roskilde. The room was a little smaller than in Esbjerg, which required moving some of the tables for the breakout sessions. In both workshops, the participants were offered smørrebrød (traditional open-faced sandwiches).

The Danish UNTWIST workshops included 17 participants across two workshops, with 10 participants in the Esbjerg workshop and 7 in the Roskilde workshop. In terms of participants' gender distribution, the Esbjerg workshop was composed of 5 men and 5 women, while the Roskilde workshop had 2 men and 5 women. Participants in Esbjerg were aged between 19 to 71 years old, participants in Roskilde between 25 to ca 70 years. The intergenerational interaction and representation were an important part of the workshop dynamics. There was considerable diversity regarding educational and socio-economic background, as well as employment status. Similarly, family status varied significantly, with participants at different life stages with various care responsibilities.

Political distribution was deliberately mixed, to enable dialogue across political positions. The Esbjerg workshop included two participants from previous right-wing populist focus groups. The Roskilde workshop also maintained political diversity, although overall it clearly had a more progressive orientation. In sum, there were three participants who placed themselves to be on the radical left (Enhedslisten), seven on the mainstream left (5 Social Democrats, 2 Ecologist), five on the mainstream right (3 Venstre, 2 Liberal Alliance), and two RWPP.

3.5.1. Policy Areas

The most prominent discussion, through the prompts but also participants' own discussions, was on the health topic. There was also significant focus on labour market issues that went well beyond what was prompted in the workshop format; participants

raised concerns about job security, workplace culture, and the relationship between education and employment – for example in the form of vocational education. Gender dynamics in the workplace emerged as a major workshop theme, both spontaneously and through prompts. Participants engaged at some depth about workplace diversity, hiring practices, and gendered employment experiences. Other main discussion points included climate and environmental concerns, but with significant regional variation.

Family issues came up primarily through prompted discussion but quickly moved into discussion of work-life balance challenges. It should be noted that two topics were generally not being engaged with, despite both prompting and encouragement: education and identity, across both workshops.

Democratic participation also emerged as an overarching theme, without prompting as such. Participants discussed how citizens can influence policy beyond voting and expressed frustration with political responses. In this context, the workshop itself became a subject of spontaneous reflection and discussion. Participants commented (positively) on the experience of engaging with strangers across political differences, expressing surprise at finding common ground and appreciation for democratic dialogue. As one participant put it: *“I think it's been really interesting that even though we come from such different backgrounds and have such different stories, we can still agree and disagree but talk to each other.”*

Overall, there were many interesting and relevant discussions in the workshop, and in themselves they seemed to have been a rewarding and positive experience for the participants. Unlike the focus groups where the homogenous composition reinforced attitudes, the workshops showed that diverse political composition can shift dialogue from reinforcement to engagement. Participants reflected on this themselves, expressing surprise at finding common ground with strangers holding opposing views.

Perhaps not surprisingly, the participants in both workshops found proposing solutions more difficult than identifying problems. This relates to both the complexity of identifying appropriate solutions and determining who should be responsible for implementing change. When the moderators asked participants to reflect on solutions, one participant acknowledged: *“the solution proposals just aren't quite there, unfortunately. I would happily fill everything with solutions, but they also need to be realistic.”*

The moderators introduced solution categories and agents of change during workshop discussions, prompting participants to consider who should act (e.g. individuals, civil society, political parties, education, protest). However, participants consistently pointed to

formal political institutions. As one Esbjerg participant stated directly: *"it should be our parliament and municipal council"*. This orientation toward state-level action appeared across both workshops, reflecting institutional and cultural traditions in Denmark.

With regards to differences between workshops and the previously held focus groups, a notable difference was that explanatory frames differed between the two formats. Focus group participants often attributed problems to individual shortcomings, cultural differences, or political elites. Workshop participants engaged more with institutional failures and systemic constraints instead. The differences were also clear with regard to the gender dynamics. The all-male focus groups displayed resentment towards gender equality; mixed-gender focus groups discussed motherhood through essentialist lenses. The workshops debated workplace diversity policies, quotas, and structural discrimination without reducing gender to one particular position.

The survey data broadly corroborate the workshop discussions in terms of problem identification. Participants in both formats identified similar systemic challenges facing Danish society, including welfare state retrenchment, pressures on healthcare provision, and immigration-related tensions. This convergence suggests a degree of consensus across methodological approaches regarding the primary policy topics requiring attention.

Both workshops discussed changes in how Danish society and media discusses gender in leadership and professional contexts could come about. They suggested media and public discourse should stop prefacing women's professional identities with gender markers (e.g., "female doctor") and should cease focusing on women leaders' appearance rather than their competence.

It is worth noting that the focus groups reinforced existing views, for example anti-immigration sentiment and patriarchal attitudes were amplified, as participants advocated collective punishment for immigrants and dismissed politicians promoting integration as naïve. The workshops show constructive disagreement. Political diversity meant participants encountered opposing views, forcing engagement with alternative perspectives rather than reinforcement of existing positions.

Healthcare

Healthcare was central in the discussions in both workshops. In Roskilde, a participant who is a nurse spoke about her professional experience: understaffing creating impossible workloads, leading to a situation where workplace stress is driving people from the profession (*"people are leaving the profession"*), declining applications to nursing programmes, wages inadequate to professional responsibility, and administrative requirements that prevented actual care work. This was also discussed in the context of

migrant labour and initiatives by municipalities to cover care needs. Healthcare discussions generated proposals for structural reform. For dental care, participants suggested either including dental treatment into the public healthcare system or implementing price caps to ensure equal access regardless of location. Healthcare solutions generated broad agreement across political positions. Both workshops supported structural intervention: better staffing, adequate wages, reduced administrative burden. For dental care access, participants either argued for public provision or price regulation.

More generally, both workshops and focus groups identified the Danish healthcare system as a central concern: understaffing, inadequate resources, less access to care, particularly elderly care and dental services.

Labor market, diversity and work-life balance

Welfare state retrenchment also was a shared issue discussed across both workshops and focus groups. Labour market concerns came up in both contexts, for example through job security, workplace conditions, and work-life balance.

Both workshops included debate about workplace diversity, and gender equity in recruitment. Female participants tended toward institutional and systemic critique of workplace discrimination and democratic deficits, while male participants focused more on economic aspects and pointed to institutions for solutions. Some participants worried that diversity initiatives prioritise representation over competence. Others argued that women hired through diversity programmes potentially face questioning of their qualifications regardless of actual merit. In the Roskilde discussion, participants disagreed on whether quotas undermine or enable merit-based selection. In Esbjerg, participants talked about resentment amongst male colleagues who might feel "*disadvantaged*" through diversity policies, potentially damaging workplace culture. These discussions came both through prompts, and participants' experiences.

Work-life balance was another problem discussed in the workshops, i.e. reconciling paid employment with care responsibilities. There was focus on assumptions about maternity leave and caregiving, as well as the economic pressure of the wage gap, and hiring discrimination of women. Participants discussed the recent earmarked paternity leave policy in Denmark which is meant to distribute care work more equitably. Some participants noted this was forced - "*make the man take it*" - rather than genuinely transforming care culture. These disagreements were aligned with a general left-right divide but not with a clear party-level divide. There was also reference to challenges when people have simultaneous responsibilities for ageing parents and children.

For workplace challenges, participants identified specific institutional mechanisms in Danish labour markets. Solutions included contacting workplace safety representatives or shop stewards, engaging with trade unions, escalating concerns through management hierarchies, or bringing issues to workplace boards. In the Esbjerg workshop, one participant pointed to the perceived limits of institutional strategies: *"If you can't go further than the leader, you're basically checkmate. So you either have to leave the workplace, or you have to swallow some things. So I think it's actually difficult when it comes to solutions."* In the Roskilde workshop, participants also discussed other collective action strategies, but also acknowledged practical difficulties when leadership itself was the problem.

Workplace diversity discussions and solutions provoked clear disagreement. Quotas divided participants in both workshops; some saw them as necessary correction for structural discrimination, others as undermining merit-based selection. The debate remained constructive albeit with clear disagreements which were not following party lines.

Climate

"So that's why I also think about the climate we've just been discussing. [...] So I feel a kind of powerlessness. Damn it [for pokker]. You keep hitting a duvet, and it won't go flat. Nothing really happens. So again. And who should take care of it then? There must be someone who can look far beyond the world's borders. So it's not just little Denmark we're doing something good for."

The climate discussions in both workshops showed geographical differences between workshop locations: in Esbjerg, participants voiced scepticism about Denmark's climate policy (there is a large offshore industry in Esbjerg), while Roskilde participants more openly engaged with possibilities for climate action. Across both workshops, however, participants raised concerns about the costs and feasibility of green transition, questions about democratic legitimacy in climate policymaking, and frustration with political failures to implement meaningful change despite rhetoric. These discussions were mainly prompted through the climate topic.

The tensions between individual responsibility and systemic change were emerging particularly while discussing this theme. Some participants expressed "powerlessness" about Denmark's capacity to influence global climate outcomes. There was some focus on individual behaviour, such as waste sorting and sustainable consumption patterns. In Esbjerg, participants argued Denmark should be the primary focus before addressing international environmental commitments.

Climate policy showed regional and political divides. Some participants in Esbjerg questioned Denmark's climate commitments as economically damaging and globally

insignificant; while others disagreed significantly. Roskilde participants engaged with climate action in more agreement, though both workshops struggled with individual versus systemic responsibility.

Democratic participation

Without prompting, participants in both workshops raised concerns about democratic participation beyond voting. They expressed frustration with political unresponsiveness, describing experiences where citizens are “heard” but ignored in actual policymaking. The workshop format itself was reflected on, with participants commenting positively on the rare opportunity for substantive dialogue across political differences. Distrust of and distance to political institutions also showed up in both focus groups and workshops, albeit more pronounced in the focus groups.

Integration policies

One of the prompted themes was that of immigration, given its relevance in the RWPPs rhetoric across countries in Europe. As expected, immigration and integration generated the deepest disagreements, with fundamental discussions about whether integration was achievable, or even desirable, in Esbjerg. To tackle the perceived issue, in Esbjerg several participants proposed more intensive Danish language classes combined with work-related language training.

Vocational education

“The state should look at itself in terms of what they did some years ago. They went in and said we need academics. [...] Fine, so they restructured the whole school system to push children into gymnasium... [...] Now they've raised the grade requirements for gymnasium so more apply for technical school. But that's coercion more than desire.”

Discussions around education generated proposals for structural reform as well. With regard to this theme, participants called for the state to reconsider how technical and vocational education is discussed publicly, for instance pointing to negative consequences of policy changes requiring higher gymnasium entry requirements to incentivise young people to take vocational education.

3.5.2. Takeaways

In terms of policy recommendations from the project outcomes overall, it is clear that the participants' discussions on healthcare and elderly care across both focus groups, and the workshops suggests welfare state dismantling produces specific gendered and classed grievances that right-wing populism uses politically but doesn't address. Rather than focusing on RWPP votes as cultural backlash, these material concerns need to be addressed as such.

In terms of policy recommendations, the findings from the workshops can be translated into the following points:

- **Healthcare Reform:** increased staffing ratios and wages; recognition of healthcare workers; reduced administrative burden preventing care work; better dental care (either integrated to public healthcare, or caps).
- **Workplace Equity** through diversity policies through e.g anonymous CV screening in public/large private sectors; strengthen existing Danish labour market institutions with discrimination mandates; eliminate gender markers in professional discourse.
- **Inclusive climate governance policy:** Just transition strategies for fossil fuel-dependent regions (Esbjerg); citizen assemblies with binding influence on climate policy; enforceable parliamentary targets shifting responsibility from individuals to institutions.
- **Integration Policies:** expand Danish language programmes with sector-specific workplace modules; strengthen labour market anti-discrimination enforcement.
- **Vocational Education:** expand publicly funded apprenticeships with living wages; change public discourse to value and acknowledge vocational training.

3.6. UK

The workshops were held in Manchester in May 2025, a time of considerable political and economic turbulence in the UK. While the UK has traditionally been characterised as a two-party system dominated by the centre-left Labour Party and centre-right Conservative Party, the last ten-fifteen years has seen increasing fragmentation. In the 2024 general election, the right-wing populist party (RWPP) Reform UK achieved a historic breakthrough, winning 14.3% of the vote and securing five parliamentary seats- an unprecedented result

for a RWPP in the UK. Reform UK emerged from the remnants of the United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP), which had previously dominated the populist right throughout the 2000s and early 2010s. While UKIP was largely defined by its Euroscepticism and anti-immigration position, Reform UK more closely resembles RWPPs in continental Europe.

The workshops took place shortly after local elections in England in which Reform UK made further significant gains, winning a majority of council seats, as well as mayoral elections and a parliamentary by-election. These results dealt a serious blow to the Labour government, elected less than a year earlier, already facing strong and growing public dissatisfaction. Political frustration is tied to the ongoing cost-of-living crisis, which began in 2021, characterised by a significant increase in the price of everyday essentials like food and energy. After a decade of austerity policies - with cuts to public services like healthcare and social care - economic insecurity has become a central issue in public debate and has shaped perceptions of government competence. Another important and salient issue is immigration which was high in media and political discourse, particularly with regards to small boat crossings in the English Channel – a key concern for Reform UK voters.

Regarding gender-related issues such as childcare, social care, and family policy, the analysis of party manifestos shows that UK parties devote limited attention to these gender-related topics, but there are notable differences between mainstream parties and RWPPs. A qualitative review of 2024 election manifestos conducted by the Manchester team (to be published) shows that Reform UK offered slightly more concrete proposals tied to economic justice, whereas mainstream parties emphasise delivery and investment, without addressing voter's everyday needs and frustrations. Reform UK have therefore capitalised on public dissatisfaction by presenting themselves as protectors of traditional values and everyday economic concerns, particularly for older voters.

The Manchester team adapted the workshop format and discussion guide, while Deltapoll, an independent public opinion and political polling consultancy, recruited participants, facilitated the sessions and provided anonymised transcripts to the research team. This approach mirrors the method used in the focus groups, ensuring consistency across different stages of the project. Both workshops were held in a hotel in central Manchester, rather than on a university campus, to avoid overt associations with academic research that could be off-putting to right-wing populist party (RWPP) voters. Central Manchester was chosen to maintain consistency with the focus groups. While the specific venue did not appear to influence the discussion directly, the broader local context did. For example, in

the all-male group, participants made several references to ‘Cresta Court’ – a hotel being used to house asylum seekers in Greater Manchester. In the all-female group, there were discussions about rising house and rental prices in specific areas of Manchester, more widely representative of the rapidly increasing cost of living in historically underprivileged areas like industrial cities in Northern England.

The two workshops were held in central Manchester on the 21st of May 2025. The workshops were divided by gender, with one all-male group and one all-female group, each moderated by a same-sex facilitator. The men’s group included 7 participants aged between 25 and 71, while the women’s group included 8 participants aged between 21 and 79, resulting in a total of 15 participants across both workshops. Both groups were heterogeneous in employment status (managers, supervisors, public sector employees, manual workers; employed, unemployed and retired), and family status. The educational level of participants was not gathered by the Manchester team. Both workshops were composed only of participants identified as ‘switcher voters’ i.e., those who have previously voted for another party but voted for Reform UK in the 2024 general election or would consider voting for Reform UK in the next election. Mirroring the German workshops, we cannot assume that more progressive voters would have backed these recommendations in the discussions. However, recommendations derived from the UK workshops overlap with recommendations from other countries where more mainstream voters were present.

3.6.1. Policy Areas

The participants engaged in discussions over a variety of topics, some prompted by the facilitators and some spontaneously emerging from the conversation, with variations between the two workshops.

Among the key spontaneous discussion points were social media and the effect it has on young people – both mental health but also encouraging crime (women’s group). In the men’s groups, negativity and anti-elitism towards politicians was one key point. Perhaps even more interestingly, in both groups two themes emerged spontaneously: immigration and issues associated with the cost of living, such as access to good housing, and problems with the National Health Service (NHS). Among the key discussion points prompted by moderators in both groups were: problems of caring for children in the context of both parents having to earn an income; decline/lack of community in the local area; and care for the elderly and who should provide this.

Participants in both groups, and especially the men's, mostly discussed issues and desired outcomes (e.g. no one uses food banks). Finding concrete solutions to these issues represented a challenge, and suggested solutions tended to focus on mitigating issues (e.g. with more apprenticeships) and not systemic change. The exception to this was in the area of social media, where the suggested solutions could be seen as fairly radical.

Some similarities emerged between the previously held focus groups and what stemmed from the workshops. Among the similarities that emerged, the perceived economic insecurity was a common discussion point, then linked to other topics too, among which the cost of living, balancing employment and family duties, and issues related to child and elderly care. Indeed, a shared concern emerged over the lack of investment in social care, albeit the workshop groups had a slightly more positive thinking on the issue, as they saw care being provided for elderly relatives in care homes, seeing these as providing more care than families could provide.

Raising and educating children was also a common topic, but while the group involved in the focus groups were more open to changes in the way children are educated, and in the greater involvement of fathers, in the workshops there was no common ground over what is the ideal way of raising children.

Concern over social media was also discussed in both focus groups and workshops, and what emerged is similar: participants were concerned about the erosion of social life caused by social media, and the negative effects it has on youth, for instance in the shape of unrealistic beauty standards and mental health.

Last but not least, concerns over the current state of the National Health System were also shared, with focus groups participants underlining the lack of investment and highlighting the impact of privatisation and immigration, while workshops participants stressed the lack of investment for staff and lacking efficiency.

Among the topics that were not discussed in the workshops but that were part instead of the focus groups were the ability of exercising civil rights and freedoms, and of being able to express sexual orientation. Civil rights and freedoms/expressing sexual orientation came up in the focus groups but discussions were brief, therefore these were not used as subsequent problem statements in the workshops. About exercising civil rights and freedoms, focus groups participants implicitly or explicitly expressed support for the idea that all have the right to an outspoken opinion. About the ability to express one's sexual orientation, instead, focus groups participants were supportive of rights for gay men and lesbian women but were also explicitly opposed to greater rights and freedoms for transgender and non-binary people.

The survey analysis in the UK highlighted that radical right voters are a little more gender-traditional in their attitudes towards men's and women's family roles than other voters. Still, workshop participants, especially the women, stressed the need for the government to provide childcare, thus enabling women to work. In the focus groups, which spent more time on this, this discussion was more nuanced; two-income families were seen as necessary rather than desirable, and if women needed to work to provide for their families, childcare needed to be available – rather than this being seen as necessarily always the best option. The surveys showed that radical right voters in the UK were more concerned about social care, particularly for the elderly, than other voters. This is mirrored by the workshop and focus group discussions where this came up as an issue of concern.

Cost of living

“Things are so expensive. Things go up and up. Mortgage rates have gone up, council tax goes up and you get bugger all for it. Do you know what I mean? Everything's going up. Prices have going up, yet things are reducing.”

The rising cost of living and the issues associated with it were a central theme in the workshops' discussions. In the women's group, the main solution proposed to tackle this situation was to increase the national minimum wage to match the living wage, which was met with full support by the attendees.

In the men's group, the main suggested solutions were to have a system for redistributing surplus food, thus alleviating the pressure of grocery shopping on low-income households, and increasing the number and quality of apprenticeships. Both solutions were supported by all the attendees.

Welfare, child and elderly care

“Like even when you've got two incomes, like one of those incomes just gets taken away by childcare, in essence”

Both child and elderly care were important themes during the workshops, especially among the women's group, and often tied to economic issues linked to the caregiving acts. Because of this, the main solutions proposed in the women's group was to have more childcare provision for working parents, including out of term time, and to allow grandparents to be paid for looking after grandchildren - and both measures were greeted with support by all the attendees.

Another discussion point that was raised spontaneously was issues related to the NHS, both in the women's and men's groups, which was introduced by participants before it could

be prompted by the moderators. Both groups directed their potential solutions towards economic adjustments to make the NHS more efficient, with the women's group suggesting to employ more staff and increase their pay, and the men's group advocating for greater cost efficiencies in the system - both solutions were met with support from the attendees.

Immigration, when raised by workshop participants, was often linked to material or economic pressures, especially pressures on social services. Addressing the state of these services – health, social care, childcare, and also education – would address a core concern for RWPP switcher voters.

Social media

“Can I borrow a screwdriver? Can you come and help me? I used to leave my door unlocked, you know you can go in your neighbour's house before and just call inside. Whereas now you got to lock your doors and as you get in and everything is social media and WhatsApp.”

“Once you don't monetize it, it stops encouraging more and more beauty standards or something that's called rage bait, where you post something that purposely makes people angry or kids upset, because you'll get more views or likes or clips and then more money. And it's not just that though, the problem with social media is if you are having a bad day or your self-esteem is already low, and you've got people like, not even influencers, if someone's having a good day and they've just bought something good and you go online, like, my life is shit.”

Social media usage and their regulation emerged as an unprompted theme in both workshops, with participants proposing what could be seen as quite radical solutions to such issues, as mentioned above.

In the women's group, the foreseen solutions were to increase the age that people could access social media to 16 or 18; to have more proof of identity required when setting up an account; and to make social media companies limit the amount of time children can spend on the site/app. All of these are quite important restrictions, and nonetheless they were all met with good support by the attendees.

In the men's group instead a ban on paying for adverts on social media - including through influencers - was suggested as the main solution to reduce harmful content as well as reduce consumerism which they saw as fuelled by social media, again met with support from the participants.

3.6.2. Takeaways

The following areas emerged from the workshops as areas for policy development:

- **Social media:** Greater regulation and control of social media, including raising the minimum age of access (currently 13 in the UK, participants suggested raising to 16/18) and requiring more stringent identity checks.
- **Health care and social care:** More investment, including in the National Health Service, elder care, and childcare. On the health service and elder care, better provision was desired, including shorter waiting times and reduction in the burden of elder care on families. On childcare, reducing costs was the main concern.
- **Addressing rising prices and living costs.**

3.7. Overview of country results

In this section, we will focus on the solutions put forward by participants. We will discuss the methodology, identify commonalities across workshops, and across the project at large.

3.7.1. Commonalities across workshops

Analysing the different solutions proposed by participants across countries, we derived five different types of measures⁶: regulation, higher public spending, cultural change, individual solution and state intervention. (1) **Regulation** is the most common proposition across topics, voiced by participants who demand more, stricter, or better regulations to improve the situation. (2) **Higher public spending** is the second most frequent type of measure, and is expressed when participants stress that higher public expenditure is the key solution to solve the issue, especially around topics of care, welfare and education. (3) **Cultural change** is less frequent, and is mentioned by participants who call for change in representations or mentality to improve a situation, especially around gender equality. (4) **Individual solution** is even less frequent, and describes participants who consider that issue should be solved by individual actions, mostly concerning the topic of safety in the public sphere. Finally, we label (5) **State interventions** are measures which should come from the state, the government or the political system, but which participants did not formulate as a clear solution.

⁶ These categories are a further elaboration based on the coding protocol for the Focus Groups (WP2) that had previously distinguished between “internal” (individual) and “external” (structural/systemic) solutions.

Despite the large representation of conservative in the workshops (see Annex i), across countries, political actions are the most common type of solution identified by participants (see Figure 1). Political actions account for 80% of all recommendations, mostly in the form of regulations (44%, 37 out of the 84 total recommendations), followed by higher public spending (25%), and other modes of state interventions (10.7%). In contrast, individual solutions make up 10.7% of all solutions, and are mostly found in Hungary where the facilitators explicitly prompted for them. Cultural change makes only 9.5% of the recommendations.

Figure 1. Percentage of solutions per type of measures for all workshops

Along with the coding categories previously used for the focus groups, we derived six key topics where workshops participants proposed solutions: (1) **Economy** (employment, labour market, inequalities ; work-life balance ; rising cost of living ; housing crisis), (2) **Migration and minorities**, (3) **Physical security**, (4) **Welfare** (healthcare system, social welfare, education, childcare), (5) **Family** (gendered roles in the family), (6) **Other** (gender sensitive language, governance, social media, climate). A detailed breakdown of solutions per type of measures, topic, and country is presented in annex ii.

As Figure 2 shows, welfare was the most important topic in the solution discussions, closely followed by economy. This highlights a strong focus on material needs and welfare state retrenchment as key priorities for participants.

no RWPP voters were present in the German workshops, we only report on measures put forward by participants which coincide with other countries' suggestions.

As for the survey and the focus groups, gender issues were mentioned while discussing other topics, especially the organisation of the labor market and the lack of childcare support. However, feminism as a cultural issue was hardly discussed across workshops.

3.7.2. Discussion on the methodology

In groups that gathered across the political spectrum, the workshops proved that very political conversations about desirable societal improvements could take place in a respectful and constructive manner. In politically mixed groups, participants voiced satisfaction with the format, and appreciated this opportunity to respectfully discuss with people who do not share their ideas, empathise with others' problems and concerns, or even come to a common understanding through discussion. This is clearly expressed by a participant in the Danish workshops:

“When I came into the room and saw who was here, I had a huge prejudice that I would probably be the only one sitting with the views I have... I expected it to be everyone against me. But I quickly discovered that's far from how it actually is, and that I've come to an agreement with many of you. It's broadened my horizon, maybe loosened some of the prejudices I have about the generations above me.”

We note that groups which gathered more conservative participants bear more similarities with the focus groups regarding the framing of the discussion than the more mixed groups politically. This may highlight that focus groups and workshops are fundamentally interactive events, where participants engage in discussions based on how others are framing issues and what are their stances on them. If participants notice others' expressions as reinforcing their views, they may be keener to express more radical views, given the absence of the implicit threat of being sanctioned by others for those views.

One of the biggest differences with the focus groups is the least focus on identity in groups that did not only gather switcher voters. In the Danish workshops, for instance, despite the team's attempts at prompting, the identity topic (including criticism of feminism) was scarcely discussed in both workshops. This can be understood as a sign that the topic was considered as too sensitive for mixed-group discussion, or as evidence that participants didn't perceive it as the most pressing concern to discuss on this occasion.

Concurring with the focus groups, gender did not stand out as a “cultural” issue in the workshops, and the emphasis was on material issues such as employment, healthcare and

housing. Participants' priority on the welfare state corroborates research suggesting a direct link between policies of austerity deregulating employment protection legislation and increased support for far-right parties (Vlandas & Halikiopoulou, 2016). As the previous section shows, the topics chosen by participants and the suggested solutions are very dependent on the local context and the dynamic of the workshop: although topics and solutions mostly converge, similar items can be voiced differently, and most solutions are at the intersection of various topics.

Interestingly, the Danish context also highlights differences between the workshops and the survey in how participants attribute responsibility for the challenges they face. Survey respondents tended to direct critique towards the EU and economic elites, while workshops' participants referred mostly to municipal or national institutions. This potential difference in attribution patterns warrants further investigation on the impact of the methodology, format and dynamic shape participants' causal narratives and accountability frameworks.

Conclusion

Deliverable 9.2 has examined the participatory workshops conducted across six European countries (Spain, Switzerland, Hungary, Germany, Denmark, and the United Kingdom) in May and June 2025 as part of the UNTWIST project. These workshops were designed to elicit citizens' everyday experiences and to explore how broader societal problems take shape in their daily lives, as well as the kinds of solutions participants prioritise. Outcomes of the workshops will support civil society organisations and political parties to make informed political decisions, in a context of political distrust towards social sciences and scepticism surrounding the practical relevance of social science methods for public decision-making among policymakers and citizens (Younger-Khan, Weidmann & Oswald, 2024). The workshops provided an opportunity for meaningful collaboration between citizens and researchers, enabling co-production of policy recommendations grounded in the project's empirical findings.

Across all national contexts, discussion was primarily centred on material concerns over cultural ones. Participants emphasised challenges in healthcare and welfare systems, cost of living, labour market conditions, and the impact of social-media-driven polarisation.

Preferred solutions overwhelmingly involved state intervention—expanded public spending, improved regulation, or structural reforms. Cultural or individual-level strategies appeared chiefly in discussions about societal recognition of care-related professions. Notably, despite differences in workshop composition, such as the more progressive, gender-conscious profiles in Germany and the inclusion of only RWPP voters in the UK, core concerns and priorities converged. This reinforces the robustness of the methodology and the capacity of participatory formats to capture cross-cutting insights across the political spectrum.

These findings align with broader project results indicating that mainstream political parties, if they aim to retain their electorates and curb the appeal of right-wing populist parties (RWPPs), must prioritise citizens’ material concerns and address deepening inequalities rather than doubling down on identitarian or cultural debates. Indeed, the workshops corroborate the expressive vote hypothesis, itself reinforced by the focus group evidence: RWPP support among switcher voters appears driven less by ideological alignment or identity-based grievances than by frustration with mainstream parties’ failure to address concrete material needs. This pattern also mirrors the literature showing that mainstream parties tend to be more responsive to the preferences of the “winners of globalisation,” while under-representing those of the “losers of globalisation”—in gendered ways (Brause & Kinski, 2024).

Importantly, the project finds no strong evidence that RWPPs offer policy solutions that better meet these material needs. Rather, RWPP gains seem propelled by their ability to articulate blame by targeting mainstream parties, institutions, or out-groups, while mainstream parties leave strategic gaps unaddressed. This dynamic raises concerns about democratic fairness and inclusiveness, as persistent under-representation of material needs undermines both legitimacy and trust. Strengthening the responsiveness of mainstream parties to the lived realities of (gendered) losers of globalisation is therefore not only normatively essential for democratic quality but may also reduce the attractiveness of RWPP narratives. When combined with effective communication strategies (see future Deliverable 10.1), such responsiveness could blunt populist blame-shifting tactics and re-anchor political debate around substantive socio-economic issues.

Another key insight from the workshops is that some of the most widely supported policy solutions fall squarely within the remit of governments: regulation, increased public investment, and forms of structural change. This places mainstream governing parties in a unique position: they can proactively set the agenda in these domains rather than reacting

defensively to RWPP-driven issue framing. Strategic agenda-setting aligned with citizens' priority areas may thus constitute a politically and democratically beneficial way forward.

At the same time, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, much of the analysis focuses on switcher voters, meaning that the salience of cultural and identity-based politics for other long-term RWPP supporters cannot be ruled out. Yet, as Downs (1957) suggests, these groups lie beyond the mainstream ideological reach, and attempting to compete with RWPPs on cultural or identitarian grounds risks alienating traditional voters. Second, while the workshops shed light on the material needs of gendered losers of globalisation, not all RWPP voters fall into this category. Subjective perceptions of threatened status—rather than objective deprivation—also matter and remain to be studied further. Third, while the workshops were positively received by participants and researchers, for several teams, the timeframe of the workshop proved too short to delve into all topics. Research involving participants over a longer time frame, as common in participatory research, would indeed allow for more in-depth exploration, which was not possible here given financial constraints. Running participatory workshops across six countries, even in this short format used in WP9, requires a significant amount of time and work from researchers, and involvement from participants which requires compensation. While participants voiced the desire to scale up such democratic practices, doing so would require considerable resources: online large scale participatory processes such as the Conference on the Future of Europe (Rosa, Guimaraes Pereira, 2025), European Citizens' Panels⁷ such as the “new European budget panel” as well as recent experiments in France (Smith, 2022) highlight how involving participants in policy making without burdening them requires reflection and funding. Finally, the diversity of methodological approaches and participants' profiles across countries, while being heuristic and more context relevant, proved challenging to harmonise results.

Overall, the participatory workshops attest to the value of anchoring citizen experiences into social research and policy deliberation. By combining participatory methods with large-scale surveys, manifesto analyses, and focus groups, UNTWIST demonstrates how mixed-method research can illuminate central social and political issues and strengthen democratic resilience. As future research continues to refine these approaches, sustained support for participatory, citizen-centred methods will be essential, both for generating high-quality scientific knowledge and for shaping political debates that resonate with the lived realities of European citizens.

⁷ https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/european-citizens-panels_en

The results presented in this deliverable focus on the local contexts and the outcome of the workshops. Upcoming Deliverable 11.7 will present a more comprehensive overview of the project's outputs at the European level.

References

- Abou-Chadi, T. (2024). A gendered far-right wave among young voters in Western Europe? *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 1(aop), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1332/25151088Y2024D000000065>
- Amacker, M., Bias, L., Rothermel, A.-K., & Nerino, V. (2024). *Deliverable 1.1 of the UNTWIST project: Typology*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14169197>
- Blassel, R., & Veronesi, L. (2025 - under evaluation). *Deliverable 9.1 of the UNTWIST project: Technical summary of the workshops*.
- Brause, S. D., & Kinski, L. (2024). Populist Party Responsiveness and Populist Party Voter Satisfaction With Democracy in Europe. *Politics and Governance*, 12(0). <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.8420>
- Carteny, G., Erbacher, R. A., & Braun, D. (2024). *Deliverable 4.2 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings WP4*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14178241>
- Downs, A. (1957). *An Economic Theory of Democracy*. New York : Harper.
- ECSA. (2015). *Ten Principles of Citizen Science – European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)*. <https://www.ecsa.ngo/10-principles/>
- Elsässer, L., & Röth, L. (2025). Fiscal implications of the populist radical right in power. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 32(3), 697–726. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2024.2314248>
- Greilinger, G., & Mudde, C. (n.d.). *Talking left, voting right*.
- Hecker, S., Wicke, N., Haklay, M., & Bonn, A. (2019). How Does Policy Conceptualise Citizen Science? A Qualitative Content Analysis of International Policy Documents. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.230>
- Lindman, C. (1989). Sources of Judicial Distrust of Social Science Evidence: A Comparison of Social Science and Jurisprudence. *Indiana Law Journal*, 64(3), Article 15.
- Lorenz, L., & Lepenies, R. (2023). *Contributions of Citizen Science to the Sustainable Development Goals: Is Transformative “Global” Citizen Science Possible? | Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.595>
- Ortiz Barquero, P., & Ruiz Jiménez, A. M. (2024). *Deliverable 2.3 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14176481>
- Rathgeb, P. (2024). *How the Radical Right Has Changed Capitalism and Welfare in Europe and the USA* (1st ed.). Oxford University PressOxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192866332.001.0001>
- Rosa, P., Guimaraes Pereira, Â., & European Commission (Eds.). (2025). *Harnessing innovation on online deliberation: Lessons learnt from the on-line citizen engagement process of the conference on the future of Europe*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/0212413>
- Ruiz Jiménez, A. M. (2024). *UNTWIST briefing 02: Strengthening Democracy By Improving Gender Representation*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14215274>

- Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Bartolomé Peral, E., & Sendra, M. (2025). *Deliverable 8.1 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings WP8* (Version 01) [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15083113>
- Ruiz Jiménez, A. M., Ortiz Barquero, P., Romero-Portillo, D., & Lara Merchán, A. (2024). *Deliverable 5.1 of the UNTWIST project: Summary of findings WP5*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14176492>
- Senabre Hidalgo, E., Perelló, J., Becker, F., Bonhoure, I., Legris, M., & Cigarini, A. (2021). Participation and Co-creation in Citizen Science. In K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 199–218). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_11
- Smith, G. (2022). Placing the Convention: An outlier amongst climate assemblies? *Participations*, 34(3), 261–281. <https://doi.org/10.3917/parti.034.0261>
- Vlandas, T., & Halikiopoulou, D. (2016). Why Far Right Parties Do Well at Times of Crisis: The Role of Labour Market Institutions. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2854926>
- Wehn, U., Ajates, R., Fraisl, D., Gharesifard, M., Gold, M., Hager, G., Oliver, J. L., See, L., Shanley, L. A., Ferri, M., Howitt, C., Monego, M., Pfeiffer, E., & Wood, C. (2021). Capturing and communicating impact of citizen science for policy: A storytelling approach. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 295, 113082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113082>
- Younger-Khan, S., Weidmann, N. B., & Oswald, L. (2024). Consistent effects of science and scientist characteristics on public trust across political regimes. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1379. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03909-2>

Annexes

i. Workshop participants political orientation

The UNTWIST project translated the MARPOR scheme into a 5-party family classification (Deliverable 8.1): right-wing populist parties, mainstream right (liberal, Christian democratic and conservative parties), mainstream left (ecological and social democratic parties), radical left (socialist and other left parties), and others. The table below reflects the composition of the participants in the workshops for each family of political parties.

	Political families					
Country	Radical Left	Mainstream left	Mainstream Right	RWPP	Others	Total
ES		PSOE (10)	PP (13)	VOX (7)		32
CH ⁸	(2)	(1)	(3)	(2)		8
HU	Opposition Coalition: DK Jobbik Momentum MSZP - LMP Párbeszéd (6) Liberals: Magyar Kétfarkú Kutya Párt (MKKP) (2)			Fidesz-KDNP (8)		16
DE ⁹						11
DK	Enhedslisten (3)	Social Democrats (5) Ecologist (2)	Venstre (3) Liberal Alliance (2)	RWPP (2)		17
UK				Reform UK (15)		15
Total						101

⁸ Swiss participants were asked to position themselves on a scale of 1 (very left) to 10 (very right). The table presents this self-categorisation. In addition, some participants stated what they voted in the last election: one participant was an SVP voter (out of the two positioning themselves on the far right), one was a GPS voter (out of the three positioning themselves on the mainstream right/left), and one was a SP voter (out of the two positioning themselves in the radical left)

⁹ German participants did not provide political positioning.

ii. Overview of participants' recommendations

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
1. Economy	Employment, labour market, inequalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increasing the minimum wage (HU) → type of measure: regulation - increasing the minimum wage (UK) → type of measure: regulation - increasing the minimum wage (ES) → type of measure: regulation - reintroducing seniority-based wage supplements (HU) → type of measure: regulation - abolishing age-based tax exemptions to ensure equal treatment by the state across age group (HU) → type of measure: regulation - Enforcing anti-discrimination / diversity policies (gender) (DK), (DE) → type of measure: regulation - progressive income tax (HU) → type of measure: regulation 			Self-development, retraining (HU) → type of measure: individual solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote stable, well-compensated employment (ES) → type of measure: state intervention - diversify the productive structure and expand equal opportunities across sectors and territories along the country (ES) → type of measure: state intervention - improving corporate responsibility and agreement between labour stakeholders (ES) → type of measure: state intervention
	Work-life balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sharing parental leave more flexibly among 			Spending more time with the family (HU) → type of	

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
		parents (CH) → type of measures: regulation - limit overtime work for parents to be able to spend more time with family (HU) → type of measure: regulation - working time reforms (DE) → type of measure: regulation - Ensure equal (50/50) parental leave (DE) → type of measure: regulation - introduce mandatory 50/50 parental leave (DE) → type of measure: regulation			measure: individual solution	
	Rise in the cost of living	- reducing VAT (HU) → type of measure: regulation - Review the adjustment between prices and wages (ES) → type of measure: regulation - Reduce taxes (ES) → type of measure: regulation			- frugal consumption (HU) → type of measure: individual solution - side jobs, job mobility (HU) → type of measure: individual solution	- Addressing rising prices and living costs (UK) → type of measure: state intervention - Addressing rising prices and living costs (ES) → type of measure: state intervention - Redistribute surplus food to alleviate pressure on low-income family (UK) → type of measure: state intervention

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
	Housing crisis	removing state incentives that distort the housing market (HU) → type of measure: regulation	- increase the availability of public or affordable housing, especially for young people and families (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending - provide housing aid (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending - Public assistance for self-reconstruction or renovation of dwellings (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending			
3. Security	Safety in public spaces	stronger law enforcement for better public safety (HU) → type of measure: regulation	better police funding (HU) → type of measure: higher public spending		- neighbourhood watch programs for better public safety (HU) → type of measures: individual solution - self-defence training for better public safety (HU) → type of measures: individual solution	
4. Welfare	Healthcare and social welfare system decline	- Improvement in resource management and the efficiency of the health system (ES) → type of measure: regulation - Improvement in resource management	- significant public investment (more staff) (HU) → type of measure: higher public spending - significant public investment (more staff) (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending	- increased recognition of healthcare workers (e.g. wages) (DK) → type of measure: cultural change - increased recognition of healthcare workers (e.g. wages) (HU) → type of measure: cultural change	Promotion of individual health-conscious behaviours such as diet and exercise as health prevention activities (HU) → type of measure: individual	Improved pension system (ES) → type of measure: state intervention

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
		<p>and the efficiency of the health system (UK) → type of measure: regulation</p> <p>- guaranteed access to a free choice of doctor. (HU) → type of measure: regulation</p> <p>- better dental care (either integrated to public healthcare, or price caps). (DK) → type of measure: regulation</p>	<p>- significant public investment (more staff) (UK) → type of measure: higher public spending</p> <p>- Increased investment in mental health care (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending</p> <p>- Extend the post-partum recovery period and improve access to mental-health services (CH) → type of measure: higher public spending</p>			
	Education	<p>increase the number and quality of apprenticeships (UK) → type of measure: regulation</p>	<p>- investment in education system (CH) → type of measure: higher public spending</p> <p>- investment in education system (ES) → type of measure: higher public spending</p> <p>- subsidise state-supported sports and healthier school meals (HU) → type of measure: higher public spending</p> <p>- Expand publicly-funded apprenticeships with living wages (DK) → type of measure: higher public</p>	<p>- change public discourse to value and acknowledge vocational training (DK) → type of measures: cultural change</p> <p>- strengthen critical thinking to equip young people with better means to disentangle confusing information both on- and offline (CH) → type of measure: cultural change</p> <p>- Awareness programmes in secondary schools to prevent bullying (ES)-> type of measure: cultural change</p>		

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
			spending - providing state-sponsored training opportunities (HU) → type of measure: higher public spending			
	Care work / child care	- more labour protection during pregnancy and motherhood (CH) → type of measure: regulation - ensure pension protection during parental leave (DE) → type of measure: regulation - reduced administrative burden preventing care work (DK) → type of measure: regulation	- expanding family benefits more fairly (HU) → type of measure: more public spending - more financial support for family and care policies (CH) → type of measure: more public spending - more financial support for family and care policies (ES) → type of measure: more public spending - improving access to elder care and cost of childcare (UK) → type of measure: more public spending - expand access to affordable childcare (DE) → type of measure: more public spending - expand state care infrastructure and improved benefits and	better recognition and pay for childcare professions (DE) → type of measure: cultural change		Family policies should focus on humans instead of on costs and economy (CH) → type of measures: state intervention

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
			allowances (HU) → type of measure: higher public spending			
5. Other	Gender sensitive language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mandatory gender-sensitive training (DE) → type of measure: regulation - eliminate gender markers in professional discourse (DK) → type of measure: regulation 				
	Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimizing the allocation and use of public resources for social impact and sustainability (ES) → type of measures: regulation - increase transparency in public administration processes (clear, accessible and accountable decision-making procedures) (ES) → type of measures: regulation - Improve coordination across levels of government and simplify administrative processes (ES) → type of measures: regulation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduce populist rhetoric by focusing on long-term achievements and promises that indicate motivation by something other than personal and short-term wins to enhance trust in the political system. (CH) → type of measures: cultural change - enforceable parliamentary targets shifting responsibility from individuals to institutions. (DK) → type of measures: culturalchange 		shifting the logic of online and offline discourse away from populist rhetoric (CH) → type of measures: state intervention

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professionalize public service and political functions to strengthen institutional capacity and governance quality (ES) → type of measures: regulation 				
	Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal consequences for online misbehaviour (CH) → type of measures: regulation - Reduce anonymity online (CH) → type of measures: regulation - Strengthen regulation and control of social media (e.g raising the minimum age of access, more stringent identity checks). (UK) → type of measure: regulation - stricter oversight on harmful online content and stereotypes (DE) → type of measure: regulation - Education regarding use of media / learning to identify false information through the state (in schools) (CH) → type of measures: regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote inclusive representation through subventions and incentives (DE) → type of measure: higher public spending 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limiting children screen time (HU) → type of measure: individual solution 	

Topics	Policy areas	Regulation	Higher public spending	Cultural change	Individual solution	State intervention
	Climate	Inclusive climate governance policy with binding influence on climate policy (DK) → type of measures: regulation		sustainable consumption patterns for individuals (DK) → type of measure: cultural change	waste sorting and sustainable consumption (DK) → type of measure: individual solution	